

A NOTE ON KJELDAHL DISTILLATION IN A CLOSED STILL

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The results of the estimation of nitrogen by Kjeldahl method are usually not concordant. One of the reasons is that ammonia evolved in the process is not completely absorbed in the acid. It is seen that the longer the period for which the ammonia remains in contact with the absorbing acid, the better the results. To elucidate this problem, a series of tests has been carried out in (a) closed still and (b) open stills. A comparative study of the two methods has been carried out, and the efficiency of the different absorbing liquids has also been studied.

Strong acids are commonly used for absorbing the ammonia. Fairly accurate results are obtained with an open type of distillation apparatus, but in this case two standard solutions are required.

Winkler (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1913, 26, 231) has introduced the use of boric acid solution for the absorption of ammonia in open still which gives nearly as accurate results as normal sulphuric acid. Boric acid solution has the advantage that it may not be measured very accurately, and only one standard solution (for titration) is required. The difficulty of judging the end-point with methyl red or congo red has been overcome by Scales and Harrison (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1920, 12, 350,) by the use of bromophenol blue. Spears (*J. Assoc. Off. Agric. Chem.*, 1921, 5, 105) and Markley and Hann (*ibid.*, 1925, 8, 455) have also reported favourably on the use of boric acid for absorbing ammonia. Stover and Sandin (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1931, 3, 240) have recommended the use of boric acid solution for absorbing ammonia even in nitrogen determination by Pregel's micro-Kjeldahl method and suggest the use of mixed indicator, methyl red-tetrabromophenol blue. Eisner, Abner and Wagner (*ibid.*, 1934, 6, 473) and Meeker and Wagner (*ibid.*, 1933, 5, 396) have suggested further improvements in the use of boric acid.

Very recently Bradley (*ibid.*, 1942, 14, 705) has suggested the use of water in closed system for absorbing ammonia and has shown that this system gives quite good results. There is, however, one practical difficulty in using water *i. e.* a very large quantity of water is required which cannot be contained in an apparatus of ordinary size.

In the present work the efficiency of the two systems of distillation—the open system in which the gases are allowed to escape and the closed system in which the gases are not allowed to escape, has been extended for the selection of the best solvent for the closed system.

The closed still was made by using a filtration flask as a receiver and closing its side arm with a balloon as described by Bradley (*loc. cit.*) and out of

400 c.c. of solution in Kjeldahl flask about 250 c.c. of the solution were recovered in an hour or 45 minutes. The flask was disconnected after the distillation but the receiving flask and the balloon were allowed to remain as such for some time longer to allow more time for the absorption of ammonia.

In excess acid method and with water, methyl red was used as indicator with the slight improvement that freshly boiled distilled water (CO₂ free) was always used. With boric acid solution a standard control solution was used to match the colour with methyl red as indicator. Colour matching presented no difficulty and no special light was used. The matching of colour was necessary due to the colour changes being gradual. It requires a little practice to perceive these colour changes. This indicator was found to be as accurate as some of the mixed indicators recommended by Stover and Sandin (*loc. cit.*) and Meeker Wagner (*loc. cit.*). In the table below are given the results obtained.

Absorbent.	Open stil old type.		Closed stil	
	Average recovery.	No. of estima- tions.	Average recovery.	No. of esti- mations.
Sulphuric acid	99.90	6	99.95	12
Boric acid	99.71	10	99.95	12
Water	99.06	10	99.85	12

From the table it is clear that the closed system gives far better results than the open system, irrespective of the solvent used. Boric acid gives as good results as sulphuric acid with the advantage that only one standard solution is required. The results with water are fairly within experimental error. But boric acid combines in itself the simplicity of operation of water and accuracy of the results of sulphuric acid.